

Theory of rare K decays

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Abstract. I review rare kaon decays. I introduce the flavor problem and possible solutions. Very rare kaon decays like $K \rightarrow \pi\nu\bar{\nu}$ are very important to this purpose: we study also $K \rightarrow \pi l^+ l^-$, $K \rightarrow \pi\pi ee$ where chiral dynamics is important to disentangle short distance effects. We discuss also the decays $K^0 \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-$, which have received recently some attention due to the measurement by LHCb.

1 Introduction and $K \rightarrow \pi\nu\bar{\nu}$

Rare kaon decays furnish challenging MFV probes and will severely constrain additional flavor physics motivated by NP [1]. SM predicts the $V - A \otimes V - A$ effective hamiltonian

$$\mathcal{H} = \frac{G_F}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{\alpha}{2\pi \sin^2 \theta_W} \left(\underbrace{V_{cs}^* V_{cd}}_{\lambda x_c} X_{NL} + \underbrace{V_{ts}^* V_{td}}_{A^2 \lambda^5 (1 - \rho - i\eta)} X(x_t) \right) \bar{s}_L \gamma_\mu d_L \bar{\nu}_L \gamma^\mu \nu_L, \quad (1)$$

$x_q = m_q^2/M_W^2$, θ_W the Weak angle and X 's are the Inami-Lin functions with Wilson coefficients known at two-loop electroweak corrections and the main uncertainties is due to the strong corrections in the charm loop contribution. The structure in (1) leads to a pure CP violating contribution to $K_L \rightarrow \pi^0\nu\bar{\nu}$, induced only from the top loop contribution and thus proportional to $\Im m(\lambda_t)$ ($\lambda_t = V_{ts}^* V_{td}$) and free of hadronic uncertainties. This leads to the prediction

$$\mathcal{B}(K_L \rightarrow \pi^0\nu\bar{\nu})_{\text{SM}} = (2.9 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-11} \quad \mathcal{B}(K^+ \rightarrow \pi^+\nu\bar{\nu})_{\text{SM}} = (8.3 \pm 0.9) \times 10^{-11},$$

where the parametric uncertainty due to the error on $|V_{cb}|$, ρ and η is shown.

Typical BSM predict new flavor structures that might affect $K \rightarrow \pi\nu\bar{\nu}$ that now can be tested at NA62 and KOTO [2]; we describe two different BSM effects i) new flavor structures for ϵ' avoiding $\Delta S = 2$ constraints (Fig. 1) [1, 3] and ii) attempts to describe B-anomalies [4], typically induce large flavor effects at $O(1)$ TeV [5]. i) the recent lattice results for $K \rightarrow 2\pi$ leave open the possibility of BSM for ϵ' ; to isospin breaking terms in $\Im(A_2)$ have been studied [3] in Fig.1. We expect effects at most 10% in $K^+ \rightarrow \pi^+\nu\bar{\nu}$ while are more sizable for $K_L \rightarrow \pi^0\nu\bar{\nu}$. Theoretically addressing flavor in Randall Sundrum models is more challenging: we have studied the so called flavor anarchy scenario with 5D MFV and custodial symmetry; the only sources of flavor breaking are two 5D anarchic Yukawa matrices. These matrices also generate also the bulk masses, which are responsible for the

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Figure 1. Impact of $K \rightarrow 2\pi$ isospin breaking terms ($\Im(A_2)$) (left) on $K \rightarrow \pi\nu\bar{\nu}$, typical effects, (right)

Figure 2. RS scenario to explain B-anomalies: $B(K \rightarrow \pi\nu\bar{\nu})$ ranges as a function of fermion profiles (c_i 's)

resulting flavor hierarchy. The theory flows to a next to minimal flavor violation model where flavor violation is dominantly coming from the 3rd generation. We show that it is possible to find a range of parameters for bulk masses satisfying experimental flavor constraints, but also we explain the neutral B-anomalies, requiring NP flavor scale at $O(1)$ TeV. Then we address $K \rightarrow \pi\nu\bar{\nu}$ -decays: we show the TH predictions as a function of the bulk fermion masses in Fig.2 [5]. A natural issue is to test $O(1)$ TeV physics at LHC; we are trying to apply the technique of Ref. [6] to this purpose.

2 $K_{L,S} \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$

Recent $K_S \rightarrow \mu\bar{\mu}$ LHCb measurement is very interesting and unexpected

$$B(K_S \rightarrow \mu\bar{\mu})_{LHCb} < 9 \times 10^{-9} \text{ at } 90\% \text{ CL} \quad B(K_S \rightarrow \mu\bar{\mu})_{SM} = (5.0 \pm 1.5) \times 10^{-12}. \quad (2)$$

It represents an important milestone since it has improved the previous limit, $< 3.2 \times 10^{-7}$ at 90 % CL, lasted 40 years. It is based on a production of $10^{13} K_S$ per fb^{-1} inside the LHCb acceptance and it is obtained using 1.0 fb^{-1} of pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 7 \text{ TeV}$ collected in 2011.

Two photon exchange generates the dominant contribution for both K_L and K_S decays to two muons [7]. The structure of weak and electromagnetic interactions entails a vanishing CP conserving short distance contribution to $K_S \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-$. Indeed the SM short diagrams (similar to $K \rightarrow \pi \nu \bar{\nu}$ in Fig. 2) lead to the SM effective hamiltonian similar to eq. (1).

The LD contributions to $K_S \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-$ Fig. (4) have been computed reliably in CHPT ($B = (5.0 \pm 1.5) \times 10^{-12}$). The relevant short distance contributions are

$$B(K_S \rightarrow \mu\bar{\mu})_{SM}^{SD} = 1 \times 10^{-5} |\Im(V_{ts}^* V_{td})|^2 \sim 10^{-13} \quad \text{vs} \quad B(K_S \rightarrow \mu\bar{\mu})_{NP} \leq 10^{-11} \quad (3)$$

We have shown that in some appealing susy scenario in Fig. (3) [8] large allowed new physics contributions (NP) can be substantially larger than SM SD contributions.

The short distance hamiltonian will contribute also to $K_L \rightarrow \mu\bar{\mu}$, through a CP conserving amplitude, $\Re(A_{\text{short}})$, that has to be disentangled from the large LD two-photon exchange contributions, $A_{\gamma\gamma}$: the absorptive LD contribution is much larger than SD, in the rate respectively 25 times larger than dispersive; total ($B_{\text{expt}} = (6.84 \pm 0.11) \times 10^{-9}$) To extract SD info the situation would be better if we would know the sign of $A_{\gamma\gamma}$, theoretically and experimentally unknown. While K_L -decays outside the LHCb fiducial volume the interference $A(K_L \rightarrow \mu\bar{\mu})^* A(K_S \rightarrow \mu\bar{\mu})$ may affect the LHCb K_S -rates: we can study the time interference $K_{S,L} \rightarrow \mu\mu$; this can be done by flavor tagging $K^0 \bar{K}^0$, specifically by detecting the associated π^\pm and (or) K^\mp , determining the impurity parameter $D = \frac{K^0 - \bar{K}^0}{K^0 + \bar{K}^0}$. Then interference term will affect the measured branching [7]:

$$\mathcal{B}(K_S^0 \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-)_{\text{eff}} = \tau_S \left(\int_{t_{\text{min}}}^{t_{\text{max}}} dt e^{-\Gamma_S t} \mathcal{E}(t) \right)^{-1} \left[\int_{t_{\text{min}}}^{t_{\text{max}}} dt \left\{ \Gamma(K_S^0 \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-) e^{-\Gamma_S t} \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + \frac{D f_K^2 M_K^3 \beta_\mu}{8\pi} \text{Re} \left[i (A_S A_L - \beta_\mu^2 B_S^* B_L) e^{-i\Delta M_K t} \right] e^{-\frac{\Gamma_S + \Gamma_L}{2} t} \right\} \mathcal{E}(t) \right], \quad (4)$$

Then we are i) increasing the sensitivity to short distance and ii) possibly determining the sign $A_{L\gamma\gamma}$

$$\sum_{\text{spin}} \mathcal{A}(K_1 \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-)^* \mathcal{A}(K_2 \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-) \sim \underbrace{\text{Im}[\lambda_t] y'_{7A}}_{SD} \left\{ \underbrace{A_{L\gamma\gamma}^\mu}_{LD} - 2\pi \sin^2 \theta_W (\text{Re}[\lambda_t] y'_{7A} + \text{Re}[\lambda_c] y_c) \right\} \quad (5)$$

Experimentally, one can also access an *effective* branching ratio of $K_S^0 \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-$ [7] which includes an interference contribution with $K_L^0 \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-$ in the neutral kaon sample.

LHCb has also a beautiful kaon physics program [10–12]

	PDG	Prospects
$K_S \rightarrow \mu\mu$	$< 9 \times 10^{-9}$ at 90% CL	(LD)(5.0 ± 1.5) $\cdot 10^{-12}$ NP $< 10^{-11}$
$K_L \rightarrow \mu\mu$	$(6.84 \pm 0.11) \times 10^{-9}$	difficult : SD \ll LD
$K_S \rightarrow \mu\mu\mu\mu$	–	SM LD $\sim 2 \times 10^{-14}$
$K_S \rightarrow ee\mu\mu$	–	$\sim 10^{-11}$
$K_S \rightarrow eeee$	–	$\sim 10^{-10}$
$K_S \rightarrow \pi^+ \pi^- \mu^+ \mu^-$	–	SM LD $\sim 10^{-14}$

Figure 3. Susy scenario: $K_S \rightarrow \mu\mu$ diagram (left), theory predictions: in dashed area no interference effects are considered (right)

Figure 4. K_S LD diagram (left), interference effect from eq. 5 on $\mathcal{B}(K_S \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-)$ depending on the $A_{L\gamma\gamma}$ sign: negative (center and in red SM while in green NP contributions) and positive (right and in blue SM while in green NP contributions).

3 The weak chiral lagrangian

In Ref. [9] we have studied how to determine the weak $O(p^4)$ chiral counterterms in

$$\mathcal{L}_{\Delta S=1} = \mathcal{L}_{\Delta S=1}^2 + \mathcal{L}_{\Delta S=1}^4 + \dots = G_8 F^4 \underbrace{\langle \lambda_6 D_\mu U^\dagger D^\mu U \rangle}_{K \rightarrow 2\pi/3\pi} + G_8 F^2 \underbrace{\sum_i N_i W_i}_{K^+ \rightarrow \pi^+ \gamma \gamma, K \rightarrow \pi^+ l^-} + \dots$$

Due to the accurate NA48/2 study of the decays $K^\pm \rightarrow \pi^\pm \pi^0 \gamma$ and $K^\pm \rightarrow \pi^\pm \pi^0 e^+ e^-$ the subset of CT's in the table can be determined

$$\begin{array}{llll}
 K^\pm \rightarrow \pi^\pm \gamma^* & N'_{14} - N'_{15} & a_+ = -0.578 \pm 0.016 & \text{NA48/2} \\
 K_S \rightarrow \pi^0 \gamma^* & 2N'_{14} + N'_{15} & a_S = (1.06^{+0.26}_{-0.21} \pm 0.07) & \text{NA48/1} \\
 K^\pm \rightarrow \pi^\pm \pi^0 \gamma & N'_{14} - N'_{15} - N'_{16} - N'_{17} & X_E = (-24 \pm 4 \pm 4) \text{ GeV}^{-4} & \text{NA48/2} \\
 K^+ \rightarrow \pi^+ \gamma \gamma & N'_{14} - N'_{15} - 2N'_{18} & \hat{c} = 1.56 \pm 0.23 \pm 0.11 & \text{NA48/2}
 \end{array} \quad (7)$$

4 $K_{S,L} \rightarrow l^+ l^-$, $K_{S,L} \rightarrow l^+ l^- l^+ l^-$ and $K_S \rightarrow \pi^+ \pi^- l^+ l^-$

Recent LHCb limit on $K_S \rightarrow \mu \bar{\mu}$ in the table is close to test interesting New Physics (NP) models. A high precision measurement can test the short distance (SD) SM but it requires to improve the long distance (LD) prediction with auxiliary channels [10]. $K_L \rightarrow \mu \mu$: the small ratio SD/LD $\sim \frac{1}{30}$ may obscure an experimental improvement on the rate. The situation would be a bit ameliorated if the sign for $A(K_L \rightarrow \gamma \gamma)$ would be known. Help to this ambiguity could come from the experimental study of $K_{S,L} \rightarrow l^+ l^- l^+ l^-$ [10] As shown in table these channels are at reach in a high intensity machine and they may also give LD distance info needed for a better control of $K_L \rightarrow \mu \mu$. These four body decays have also a peculiar feature, similarly to $K_{S,L} \rightarrow \pi^+ \pi^- e^+ e^-$, the two different helicity amplitudes interfere; then one can measure the sign $K_L \rightarrow \gamma^* \gamma^* \rightarrow l^+ l^- l^+ l^-$ by studying the time interference $K_S K_L$ which it has a decay length $2\Gamma_S$ [10].

The interplay between LHCb and NA62 program is nicely shown in ref [12].

$K_S \rightarrow \pi^+ \pi^- l^+ l^-$ Following the study of $K^+ \rightarrow \pi^+ \pi^0 l^+ l^-$ in Ref. [13] we have studied the decay $K_S \rightarrow \pi^+ \pi^- l^+ l^-$ [9], that it has been studied by NA48/2 and it is a target of LHCb. One finds that the long-distance contributions to $K_S \rightarrow \pi^+ \pi^- \gamma^*$ can be determined with remarkable accuracy, namely

$$BR(K_S \rightarrow \pi^+ \pi^- e^+ e^-) = \underbrace{4.74 \cdot 10^{-5}}_{\text{Brems.}} + \underbrace{4.39 \cdot 10^{-8}}_{\text{Int.}} + \underbrace{1.33 \cdot 10^{-10}}_{\text{DE}} . \quad (8)$$

This number is in excellent agreement with the PDG average [14]:

$$BR(K_S \rightarrow \pi^+ \pi^- e^+ e^-)_{exp} = (4.79 \pm 0.15) \times 10^{-5} . \quad (9)$$

Similarly, one can predict that

$$BR(K_S \rightarrow \pi^+ \pi^- \mu^+ \mu^-) = \underbrace{4.17 \cdot 10^{-14}}_{\text{Brems.}} + \underbrace{4.98 \cdot 10^{-15}}_{\text{Int.}} + \underbrace{2.17 \cdot 10^{-16}}_{\text{DE}} . \quad (10)$$

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